

Livable Cities Index

Tool description

The Liveable Cities Index, created by CETAQUA, measures how good it is to live in a city. It uses 75 indicators in five areas: Society, Environment, Health, Land Use, and Resources. With public city data, it creates one overall score and ranking, but you can also see results by category. This helps identify what cities are doing well and where they can improve. In short: The Liveable Cities Index turns complex data into a simple picture of city life and well-being.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

The index shows inequalities between cities, highlighting cities with less access to healthcare, green spaces, or services. This helps to focus actions where they are most needed, but its impact depends on local data and the city's commitment to act.

Procedural Justice

The index uses open data to make city planning more transparent and comparable. It helps to identify problems, guide actions, and track progress, but its impact depends on local capacity and citizen involvement to translate the index insights into suitable local interventions.

Recognition Justice

The index highlights social inequalities—like income gaps, vulnerable areas, or unemployment—while linking them to health and environmental risks. This helps cities recognize the specific needs of different communities and include them in urban planning.

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

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Tool description

The Child & Youth Friendly Urban Design (CYFUD) tool summarizes the indicators of child-friendly cities. Based on CYFUD tailored toolkits are designed to the specific requirements of each project.

During UP2030, the tool was used to design toolkits for Belfast City Council and BKK-the Budapest Transport Centre, focusing on urban design qualities along children's routes to school and aiming to engage more children in active school travel initiatives.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice	The materials included in each CYFUD toolkit are flexible and available for each Municipality, local enablers and implementors to be used across different schools and communities in the pilot project that was designed for, and beyond.
Procedural Justice	Each CYFUD toolkit is developed in collaboration with the Municipality and local implementor to ensure that specific needs are addressed and local context is taken into consideration. A range of participatory activities ensures adaptability for different resources in each participating school or different projects.
Recognition Justice	CYFUD and its tailored toolkits recognize children's right to take part in urban design and planning processes. Through a range of child-friendly participatory tools and various modes of expression, they create space for children's experiences to be heard and to inspire policymaking decisions.

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

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Tool description

The Urban Green Economy Model (UGEM) simulates the dynamics of various systems at the urban level. It covers main urban systems - buildings, transport, local energy supply, waste, water, local industry and services - including a new housing module.

With UGEM, decision-makers can simulate policy-scenarios and generate evidence for budget allocation.

The model is under development with planned implementation in Thessaloniki.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

UGEM provides evidence to better distribute budget based on dynamic simulations of interconnected urban systems.

Procedural Justice

UGEM's findings can be used to support discussions with residents, experts, and decision-makers. It can also simulate citizen-informed policy scenarios via workshops to reflect local priorities, giving voice to the community on policy decisions.

Recognition Justice

UGEM can pay special attention to vulnerable groups. For example, with the housing module, energy poverty, energy efficiency and social housing investment needs, along with different policy actions can be assessed, to target investments where they are most needed.

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

Evaluation at the end of the cycle can provide feedback on the implemented measures and policies

UGEM can be used in workshop settings with local communities to simulate citizen-informed scenarios

UGEM supports policy impact evaluation the best with modelling and scenario analysis

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Tool description

The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology uses storytelling as a way to understand the concerns, ideas and desired futures of communities on chosen topics. It follows a 4-phase process that enables citizens to express their thoughts and feelings on their living environment and their desires for the future by telling imaginaries stories that reflect real-life experiences. By analysing the metaphors citizens use in their imaginary stories, we uncover deeper insights and use these to influence the design and deployment of real life interventions.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

The methodology includes an extended process of identifying and inviting participants from diverse communities, and amplifies their voices while maintaining a focus on consensus.

Procedural Justice

The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology supports procedural justice by enabling the orientation of policy and infrastructural design to citizen perspectives and preferences. By implementing early, interventions can consider the ideas and narratives identified.

Recognition Justice

The Storytelling for Participatory Exchange methodology promotes consensus between participants allowing for reflections on intersectional needs. The analytical procedure breaks down participant contributions, acknowledging individual perspective without platforming some voices over others.

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

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Methodology: <https://www.urbanstorytelling.org/>

Tool description

Community Maps is an interactive web platform for participatory planning, community engagement, and citizen science. It enables collaborative mapping without extra programming, supported by an admin tool for easy project setup. Municipalities can share planning proposals, such as cycle routes or green infrastructure, and gather public feedback directly through the platform. For example, Budapest's City Planning Department uses it to involve citizens in shaping its Green Infrastructure Strategy.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

Community Maps address distributive justice by enabling communities, especially those frequently left out of participatory planning processes, to identify areas of concern and opportunity so that sustainability interventions can be distributed in a fair and equitable manner.

Procedural Justice

Community Maps address procedural justice by enabling early, transparent engagement in planning processes, helping build trust and showing how communities can influence decisions. It also supports monitoring interventions through data and citizen feedback.

Recognition Justice

Community Maps address recognition justice through the co-production of data, sharing of lived experiences, priorities, and local insights that can shape and contextualise planning processes.

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

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Intro to Community Maps

Tool description

The Spatial Justice Benchmarking Tool (SJBT) is a qualitative assessment framework that draws from justice theory and urban governance analysis. The tool is designed to evaluate how city strategic plans integrate Spatial Justice considerations by focusing on nine aspects linked to the three core dimensions of justice — distributive, procedural, and recognition. Each aspect can be assessed on a scale of low, starting, basic, growing, and embedded.

The tool was tested in 10 European Cities and the city of Rio de Janeiro via the analysis of their carbon-neutrality or sustainability plans.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

Supports the assessment of three aspects related to distributive justice: (1) fair allocation of burdens and benefits of urban development and sustainability transitions, (2) access in terms of easy to reach urban services and amenities, and (3) people's ability to transform and make use of available services and amenities.

Procedural Justice

Supports the assessment of three aspects related to procedural justice: (1) how people and civic society influence decision-making, (2) how institutions are adapting to the diverse needs of the citizenry, and (3) how responsive are institutions to changes in the city (proactively or reactively).

Recognition Justice

Supports the assessment of three aspects related to recognition justice: (1) validation and recognition of difference in individuals and groups - dignified treatment of all, (2) support and implementation of alternative practices for that support marginalised groups, and (3) facilitation and respect for the co-existence of different groups.

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

The tool critically assessing how justice principles were embedded throughout the planning cycle. It supports institutional learning and guides adjustments for more just future planning cycles

The tool helps to evaluate and align policy tools across the three dimensions of justice, ensuring they respond to local needs, reduce inequalities, and institutionalise fairness

The tool is used to evaluate alternative strategies against justice dimensions, promoting informed decision-making by comparing alternatives, identifying trade-offs, and selecting options that advance equitable, inclusive, and sustainable urban outcomes

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Repository

Tool description

The UDCW Facilitation toolkit is a family of participatory tools supporting knowledge sharing and co-production in a multi-stakeholder context, facilitating communication about urban climate resilience topics and bridging complex and science-based inputs with tacit knowledge. The toolkit includes: Collaborative mapping; City visions and local needs matching; "A day in the life" visioning exercise; and a 3D neighbourhood configurator tool. The tools are conceived to match urban design solutions for mitigation and adaptation with everyday practices and needs of citizens as well as with capacity building issues of public administrations and decision makers.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

- Mapping the distribution of burdens and benefits across the city and groups
- Identifying hotspot areas and setting priorities for interventions
- Linking non-climate priorities to fair allocation of urban services and infrastructure
- Highlighting intersectional injustices and vulnerabilities across different population groups

Procedural Justice

- Participatory diagnosis and early engagement in planning
- Ensuring feasibility of extended participatory activities
- Digitalizing and sharing results
- Promoting climate interventions that also enhance urban quality
- Guaranteeing fair representation of citizens in urban transformation processes

Recognition Justice

- Co-producing and sharing data
- Making visible existing injustices, exclusions, and marginalization
- Understanding vulnerabilities and their root causes
- Contextualizing climate design solutions with situated knowledge
- Building collective storytelling and supporting recognition of diverse subjectivities

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

The workshop environment of the UDCW methodology develops urban design prototypes assessing climate benefits and co-benefits and potential alternatives. It tests them in a participatory process, engaging stakeholders and communities

The toolkit provides identification and visualization of local needs and every-day issues related to climate and quality of urban space

The toolkit generates actionable insights and spatialized strategies to co-design climate-resilient interventions that are community-based

The toolkit allows visioning of desirable outcomes tailored on a specific end-user personas and on collective co-produced narratives

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Tool description

Neutrality Story Maps is a digital communication platform that fosters dialogue between citizens and policymakers on climate neutrality. Through map-based storytelling, it enables residents to share their experiences and aspirations, while helping city officials communicate climate challenges and engage communities in an accessible, narrative-driven format. By supporting two-way communication, the platform builds trust and promotes inclusive climate action.

Spatial Justice

HOW SPATIAL JUSTICE DIMENSIONS ARE ADDRESSED

Distributive Justice

The platform addresses distributive justice by unveiling the concerns and hopes of marginalized communities, potentially leading to more equitable resource distribution and policy outcomes.

Procedural Justice

Through collaborative digital storytelling, city stakeholders are actively involved and empowered in developing the maps, fostering inclusivity and procedural justice.

Recognition Justice

The platform amplifies the voices of vulnerable groups and, by centering their lived experiences in urban adaptation planning, it contributes to the recognition justice dimension.

Neutrality Story Maps

UP2030

Recommended applications in the planning cycle

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Neutrality Story Maps:

